

WEB TRAPS AND DIGITAL RESILIENCE: LEVERAGING SERIOUS EDUCATIONAL GAMES FOR CHILD SAFETY

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About ENACT

ENACT is a knowledge network focused on the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT). The network is funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme in Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society. The project addresses the call topic HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01-02 ‘Knowledge Networks for Security Research & Innovation’, aiming to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and make the most of the existing knowledge in the FCT area.

The project aims to satisfy two major ambitions,

- Provide evidence-based support to the decision-makers in the EU research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the FCT domain, targeted explicitly at enabling more effective and efficient programming of EU-funded R&I for the fight against crime and terrorism.
- Act as a catalyst for the uptake of innovation by enhancing the visibility and reliability of innovative FCT security solutions.

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<https://he-ahead-project.eu/>

Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Analytical Report
BIK+	Better Internet for Kids+
CERIS	Community of European R&I for Security
CSA	Child Sexual Abuse
CSAM	Child Sexual Abuse Material
CSEA	Children Sexual Exploitation and Abuse
DSA	Digital Services Act
EU	European Union
FCT	Fight against Crime and Terrorism
FR	Flash report
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency
OPSC	Optional Protocol on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution, and Child Pornography
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
UNCRC	United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child
WP	Work Package

Introduction

The ubiquitous integration of the Internet in daily life has created both opportunities and risks, particularly for younger users who often lack awareness of the dangers associated with unregulated digital activity. As a result, children are rather susceptible to *web traps*—malicious tactics designed to exploit personal data, financial resources or psychological vulnerabilities. These threats include, but are not limited to, phishing schemes, grooming, radicalization pathways, and social engineering tactics, all of which endanger young individuals in online environments.

The evolving threats presented are often disguised within everyday online experiences. Specifically, teenagers are increasingly exposed to harmful content through online gaming and memetic culture (both expressed using softened language and humour) which can serve as gateways to radicalization, cyberbullying, and exploitation [1]. The metaverse and livestreaming platforms further complicate online safety, as they enable the rapid spread of problematic content, ranging from self-harm promotion and violent extremism to child sexual exploitation and abuse (CSEA) materials [2]. Additionally, unsolicited sexting and sexual exploitation on dating platforms pose significant risks, often occurring without parental knowledge or adequate platform moderation [3]. Another growing concern is the permanence of shared content, as anything uploaded online can resurface unexpectedly, leading to long-term consequences such as bullying, reputational damage, or even legal implications (e.g., sexual deepfakes) [4]. These concerns are reflected in growing public anxiety. In a recent survey, 55% of surveyed parents ranked online safety as their primary concern, surpassing worries about their children's mental and physical health [5].

This brings into focus the pressing need for preventive measures, so that parents and young users are well informed and equipped with the know-how and tools to make educated decisions in each and every online interaction, rather than acting after the harm has been inflicted. This report aims to evaluate existing and new efforts towards preventing web traps, with special emphasis on *serious educational games* and similar preventive digital tools. The report falls under three primary pillars: (i) The policy view that examines and outlines the manner of online safety measures dictated by regulatory frameworks, (ii) The technology view that studies the development and use of tools, digital literacy initiatives, and serious educational games with the purpose of educating young users and parents on how to steer clear of online dangers securely, and (iii) The ethical, legal and societal view that examines the acceptability, compliance, and social implications of these solutions, guaranteeing that they are consistent with legal frameworks, ethical standards, and public confidence, particularly with law enforcement agencies (LEAs), parents, and young users.

Statistical analysis of ENACT's structured knowledge base

As part of ENACT's mission to consolidate and leverage existing knowledge in the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT), we conducted a thorough data collection and characterisation process according to the EU Civil Security (EUCS) Taxonomy [6] developed by the European Commission under the EU Security Market Study released in 2021. Our analysis revealed a cluster of observations highly relevant to the thematic focus of this report, which are catalogued in ENACT's structured knowledge base (SKB). We identified several observations directly related to "web traps" (identification, analysis, mitigation, monitoring, and others) as well as to serious educational games (development, best practices, evaluation, impact assessment, and others). Additionally, several indirectly related observations (such as cybersecurity training, child empowerment methods, digital parenting resources) were considered to provide a holistic perspective on the subject matter.

Figure 1 showcases the classification of each observation under the EUCS policy taxonomy, noting that a single observation may be relevant to more than one category. It can be observed that the majority of observations are related to Cybercrime and Horizontal and Societal issues, highlighting the growing relevance of these areas in the context of security threats, technological advancements and policy considerations.

Figure 1 - Classification of observations related to "web traps" and serious educational games.

To better understand the intersections and relationships between Cybercrime and Horizontal and Societal Issues within ENACT’s SKB, we employ an UpSet plot [7]. Figure 2 focuses on the two most prominent EUCS subcategories within each category: Online identity theft and Child sexual abuse for Cybercrime, and Disinformation and fake news and Hate speech for Horizontal and Societal Issues.

Figure 2 - Associations between SKB’s observations related to “web traps” and serious educational games.

Figure 3 showcases the mapping of the observations in the SKB that are relevant to the thematic topic according to EUCS Taxonomy Functions. The primary functions are related to "Training and exercises" along with “Secure and public communication, data and information exchange”, “Data, information & intelligence gathering management, and exploitation”, and “Investigation and forensics”.

Figure 3 - Mapping of the SKB’s observations according to the EUCS Taxonomy Functions

Finally, in Figure 4 we perform similar analysis targeted towards establishing the relevance of observations according to EUCS Taxonomy Technologies. Specifically, “Digital security products and services” is naturally linked with the topic of “web traps” and serious educational games with the technologies of “Training and Simulation”, “Data analytics” and “Monitoring tools and services” following closely by.

Figure 4 - Mapping of the SKB's observations according to the EUCS Taxonomy Technologies)

Policy View

Sexual abuse of children is a phenomenon that the international Community has paid increasing attention to [8]. This is important because the person who has been abused carries these experiences throughout their lives. The consequences of exploitation are both psychological and economic losses for society.

In this section, we will focus on the EU and international Strategy-level expressions written on the topic.

European Union Policy trends

EU Strategy for a More Effective Fight Against Child Sexual Abuse (2020-2025) – Strengthens EU-wide legal measures to combat CSA

The EU Strategy [9] aims to combat child sexual abuse (CSA) by utilising legislative, coordination, and funding tools. It focuses on three areas: stronger law enforcement, better victim support, and improved prevention. The strategy outlines eight initiatives, including ensuring full implementation of existing laws (e.g., Directive 2011/93/EU), closing legislative gaps, enhancing law enforcement efforts, supporting prevention, establishing a European centre for abuse prevention, and engaging industry and global stakeholders in child protection.

Digital Services Act (DSA) – 2022 Requires online platforms to remove illegal content, including CSAM (child sexual abuse material)

The Digital Services Act (DSA) aims to enhance online safety, particularly for children, by addressing illegal content such as child sexual abuse material and unsafe products. It includes measures to empower users to report illegal content, introduce trusted flaggers to help remove harmful material, and enforce stronger protections against online exploitation. The DSA mandates platforms to ensure the privacy and security of minors, bans targeted advertising based on profiling children, and enforces transparency in online content moderation. It also holds large platforms accountable for their role in preventing harms to vulnerable users, including children.

International Policies & Frameworks

The UN has also taken the matter seriously and observed it globally, but also through different crises (United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) – 1989, Article 34: Protection from sexual exploitation and abuse. Article 35: Prevention of child trafficking)

Optional Protocol on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution, and Child Pornography (OPSC) – 2000 describes how the Convention on the Rights of the Child recognizes the child's right to protection from economic exploitation and harmful work. It expresses concern over increasing international child trafficking, sex tourism, and the widespread availability of child pornography, especially online. It highlights the heightened vulnerability of girls and the need for a holistic approach to combat these issues, addressing root causes like poverty, gender discrimination, and armed conflict. The importance of public awareness, stronger global partnerships, and improved law enforcement is emphasized, alongside the need for adherence to international legal instruments protecting children.

Council of Europe Convention on the Protection of Children Against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse (Lanzarote Convention, Comprehensive framework for criminalizing CSA, ensuring victim support, and international cooperation) – 2007 describes, how the member States of the Council of Europe recognize the need for stronger protection of children from sexual exploitation and abuse, including child pornography and prostitution, which harm their health and development. Given the rise of such exploitation, especially through ICTs, international cooperation is essential. The well-being of children is a shared value, and the Council of Europe has previously adopted actions and recommendations to combat these issues, including frameworks on trafficking, cybercrime, and child protection. The goal is to establish comprehensive international measures for prevention, protection, and criminal justice, with effective monitoring mechanisms.

WeProtect Global Alliance (2014, ongoing) is a coalition of governments, tech companies, and NGOs fighting online child sexual abuse and exploitation. The Global Alliance Against Child Sexual Abuse Online, launched on 5 December 2012, aims to combat online sexual crimes against children globally. Its members commit to improving victim protection, prosecuting offenders, raising awareness, and reducing child pornography online. Countries participating in the Alliance have pledged to focus on four key areas: victim identification and support, investigating and prosecuting offenders, increasing awareness, and reducing child pornography availability. Members also commit to taking concrete actions to achieve these goals, based on their specific national contexts.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 16.2) – 2015 calls for an end to abuse, exploitation, trafficking, and violence against children. Violence against children includes all forms of harm by parents, caregivers, peers, or strangers, and affects an estimated 1 billion children globally. It can be physical, sexual, emotional, or neglectful, and can occur in homes, schools, or online. Violence has lifelong effects on health and well-being, contributing to injuries, mental health issues, and even death. It also impacts future opportunities and can perpetuate cycles of violence. Target 16.2 of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development aims to end all forms of violence against children, and evidence shows that prevention is possible.

FCT Policy

Interpol's Crimes Against Children Unit works globally with the CSEM topic. Children worldwide face dangers like sexual abuse, exploitation, trafficking, forced labour, and abduction. INTERPOL address these international crimes by issuing Yellow Notices to trace missing children and collaborating with member countries to rescue victims. The rise of the Internet has facilitated the spread of child sexual abuse material, with offenders using social networks and live videos to exploit children. Our priority is to identify and rescue victims, block abusive material, and prevent offenders from escaping justice by travelling abroad [10].

Strategy and Policy

Spain Proposes Law to Shield Children from Online Threats

Spain's government has introduced a proposal aimed at protecting children from online dangers, including raising the minimum age for social media use from 14 to 16, mandatory age verification tools, and virtual restraining orders for online offenders. The law would criminalize sharing pornographic content with minors and creating AI-generated sexual deepfakes. It also mandates teacher training, public awareness campaigns, and mental health screenings for teens.

A Digital Decade for children and youth: the new European strategy for a better internet for kids (BIK+)

The Better Internet for Kids+ (BIK+) strategy updates the EU's 2012 initiative to ensure children are protected, respected, and empowered in the digital world. In line with the EU's Digital Decade goals, BIK+ addresses the growing online presence of children, especially those in vulnerable situations, and aims to reduce digital inequalities highlighted by the COVID-19 pandemic.

BIK+ supports children's rights online through safer digital spaces, improved digital literacy, and equal access to technology. It builds on the Digital Services Act and reflects EU values like child protection and empowerment. Developed through broad consultations, BIK+ complements national efforts and the EU Strategy on the Rights of the Child by helping children safely participate and thrive in the digital environment.

Technology View

The protection of children in online spaces has been an issue of appropriate application development and platform design for several years. Traditional solutions have ranged from efficient content moderation to age verification, data protection laws, and AI-based detection systems. While conventional approaches provide valuable safeguards in ensuring children's safety while navigating the Internet, they also present challenges and limitations, particularly in addressing dynamic threats without the users' losing privacy or digital autonomy.

AI-based content moderation is marred by false positives, context misinterpretation, and delayed responses, while age verification systems remain too easily evaded or intrusive, raising privacy concerns. End-to-end encrypted chat applications, although protecting privacy, also bar the detection of online grooming and Child Sexual Abuse Material (CSAM). Survivor-informed and collaborative platform design aid in the development of online safe spaces particularly in AI-driven and VR environments, where conventional moderation approaches may fall short. Aside from risk detection, digital well-being features like screen time management features, grayscale modes to inhibit digital stimulation, and reducing number and frequency of notifications restrict compulsive use and potentially unsafe behaviour. Finally, parental controls are beneficial for monitoring and content filtering but require a balanced strategy taking into account children's digital freedom as well as ensuring their security. While strictly technical solutions aid in combating accidental misuse of online platforms by children, serious educational games offer a proactive approach to equipping children with the knowledge and skills needed to handle online threats effectively.

The development of serious games to support children and young people in understanding online and cyber risks is a hot topic with many education products and services available. This topic is also highly prevalent in scientific research. The Better Internet for Kids (BIK) [11] initiative alongside Safer Internet Day [12] (11 February) provide a platform for the dissemination and cataloguing of numerous resources related to internet safety, including serious games. ENACT identified 89 different games, published since 2020, relating to different aspects of online safety and targeted at children and young people. The games had different formats, the majority were online – interactive games played either through a web browser, a mobile application or embedded into another game (~65%), quiz-type games also featured in 10% of games, while 24% of the games were offline games. Virtual reality-type games are, at the moment, underexplored in this area.

In terms of topic, over 30% focused generally on online safety and 16% on cyber security; however, there were several games that targeted specific online threats or risks including cyber bullying, digital skills, privacy and online well-being. Media literacy also features prominently with around 20% of the available games focusing on media literacy in general or more specifically on fake news, misinformation, disinformation and propaganda. Various aspects relating to sex and relationships including grooming, child sexual abuse, and sextortion also featured in around 10% of available games. Other adjacent topics that were the subject of one or two games included online radicalisations, cybercrime, algorithms and online gaming.

The games themselves, while focusing on online safety topics, are typically not utilising advanced technology but serve to inform children, young people and sometimes parents and teachers about potential online risks. In general, online games and quizzes were intended to be played by a single player, while many of the offline games were designed to be played by families or in a classroom setting.

In terms of the game developers and game providers, across Europe many of the games have been developed in collaboration with the Safer Internet Centres of the Member State or a similar child protection agency. Many large organisations have also made games available including AdWiseOnline 2025 [13] as part of the BIK initiative, Google with Interland [14] and SpaceShelter [15], UNICEF – with Ask Me, the FBI with FBI SOS16, NCMEC with Cloud Chaos [17], as well as police forces and cyber security centres.

It appears that few European-funded projects are focusing on explicitly developing serious games for online safety specifically targeted at children and young people. Two exceptions to this are RAYUELA [18] and Extremimus [19] which focus on cybercrime and online radicalisation/hate speech respectively. The game developed by RAYUELA has been made available by the Polícia Judiciária [20] for use in Portugal while other versions are available from the website [21].

Serious games for online safety are also a highly relevant topic in research, in this case articles focus not only on the design and development process but also, where possible, evaluating the efficacy of serious games for educating child and young people about online risks. Unfortunately, not all games developed within the context of scientific research have been made more broadly available. Nonetheless, recent articles of specifically relevant to this topic include the development and evaluation of May and Bay [22] which focused more specifically on online child abuse and exploitation in Southeast Asia. Other scientific articles also consider other perspectives such as how to create empathy in cases of cyber bullying [23] and an overview of serious games for cyber bullying in general [24], which found only some games appeared to be effective.

Ethical, Legal, Societal view

Protecting children and vulnerable groups, online and offline, is a central ethical, legal, and societal goal. Providing suitable mechanisms to ensure that children and adolescents can fully develop their potential is of pivotal importance. It has already been understood that children protection is a concern of the whole society and not limited to the parents and family. Thus, beyond moral norms guiding our society, the State also plays a main role in establishing regulations to protect children. With the world digitalisation, these debates also migrate to the use of internet and technologies. Digital participation became a great part of the discussion, following the understanding that accessing digital platforms, media, and content is also important for a full social and intellectual development. However, as already mentioned, the risks of manipulation, frauds, radicalisation, psychological damages, various abuses, among others, can easier become real damages. This report will present the main ethical and societal issues and solutions already mapped and relevant legal framework.

Critical ethical and societal issues

Education is of utmost importance to avoid web traps. This process involves participation and programs envisioned to parents [25, 26], families [27], educators [28], but also children and adolescents themselves [29]. For this, various projects and materials were already developed [30, 31], representing the majority of relevant observations (approximately 35%). Nonetheless, different challenges remain, as the lack of a harmonious approach (e.g., federal states, different contexts and languages), limited time and resources [32]. Furthermore, research is already available about the consequences of being hyperconnected to young people. Nonetheless, these results vary and are still limited, especially because while it is important for young people to be connected, this already represents risks to the group, and excess of connectivity may raise other concerns as addiction and isolation [33-35]. This illustrates the need for further investigation and projects on relevant topics for children protection online, what will also serve as reference and provide recommendations for better designed legal norms.

EU and MS legal framework

An important piece of regulation for combating web traps is the Child Sexual Abuse Material (CSAM) proposal. Currently, the norm has not yet been adopted by the European Union, but debates about the provisional text are already in full motion [36], especially because this norm carries a lot of controversy. While the objective of the law, which is to prevent and combat child sexual abuse, is not in dispute, the technical solutions imposed by the proposal are. For the mentioned goal, the proposed Regulation would impose break of cryptography and screening of conversations in digital platforms to investigate potential crimes and abuses. However, said actions directly affect other fundamental rights, such as personal data protection and privacy. Also, these remedies do not solve other issues related to CSAM distribution, for example, AI-generated videos of child sexual abuse [37]. Nonetheless, member-states are also working on national laws for children protection, with specific provisions (e.g., virtual restraining orders) [29, 38]. While national initiatives are crucial to better address regional contexts and consider cultural aspects, lack of harmonisation can be a challenge for proper adherence to legal provisions.

Beyond specific laws related to combating CSAM, other legislations already in force are used to protect the interests and security of young audience. The Digital Services Act (DSA) has already been used as a basis for the EU Commission to open a formal investigation into TikTok, focused on data protection [39]. The Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) also becomes of utmost importance in the debate involving deep fakes and AI generated content. Although there are no observations with a sole focus on evaluating the applicable legal framework, the 2024 “New Better Internet for Kids Strategy” Report by the European Commission [40] offers a list of laws in force [41], proposals, and soft laws in the EU for children protection in the digital world. Dissemination activities around these laws can be a useful topic for a research project, considering the benefits knowledge around existing rights can bring to different societal groups.

Highlights

The 22nd Safer Internet Day [42] was celebrated on February 11, 2025, with initiatives revolving around the launch of educational games with a specific focus on responsible AI use. Many influential partners and organizations supported the annual celebration, such as UNICEF, the United Nations, Google, YouTube, and Minecraft.

Following that, a virtual summit organized by Children at Risk in March 2025 [43], examined emerging threats and prevention strategies in the digital age while also providing practical tools to protect young users from online exploitation. Additionally, the National Internet Safety Month [44], observed annually in June, is a dedicated period for raising awareness about online safety and promoting responsible internet usage among families and kids.

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A.1 Serious Games for Online Safety

Title	Type	Main Topics	Developer	Link
Fake it to make it - web-based game about fake news and disinformation	online - interactive	fake news; disinformation	Better Internet for Kids / Portuguese SIC	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/fake-it-make-it-web-based-game-about-fake-news-and-disinformation https://www.pt.fakeittomakeitgame.com/ (Portuguese)
L1V14 Online Escape Room	online - interactive	media literacy	Better Internet for Kids / KAVI	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/pedagogical-material-l1v14-online-escape-room https://mediataitokoulu.fi/materiaalipankki/mediakasvatuksen-verkkopakopeli/ (Finnish) https://mediataitokoulu.fi/sv/materiaalipankki/rymningsspel-for-mediefostran/ (Swedish)
Quiz “Sex, diversity and porn”	online - quiz	sex and relationships	Better Internet for Kids / Austrian SIC	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/quiz-sex-diversity-and-porn https://www.riddle.com/view/LguUmzB8 (German)
AdWiseOnline 2025	online - interactive	digital marketing	Better Internet for Kids	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/adwiseonline
DigiStories: Alex	online - interactive	online wellbeing	Better Internet for Kids / People In Need	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/digestories-alex https://www.jsns.cz/lekce/1506342-digestories-alex (Czech)
Cyber Escape Room (Küberpõgenemistuba metoodika ja sisu)	online - interactive	cyber security	Better Internet for Kids / Estonian Union for Child Welfare	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/kuberpogenemistuba-metoodika-ja-sisu-cyber-escape-room-methodology-and-content https://www.targaltinternetis.ee/uudised/2024/05/targalt-internetis-kuberpogenemistuba/ (Estonian)
Just Kidding (Läppä lentää)	online - interactive	cyber bullying	Better Internet for Kids / Mannerheim League for Child Welfare	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/lappa-lentaa-just-kidding-interactive-learnig-game https://www.mll.fi/tehtavat/lappa-lentaa-peli/ (Finnish)
Quiz for young people on sex, diversity and porn	online - quiz	sex and relationships	Better Internet for Kids / Landeszentrale für Medien und Kommunikation (LMK) Rheinland-Pfalz	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/quiz-young-people-sex-diversity-and-porn https://www.klicksafe.de/en/materialien/quiz-zum-thema-sex-diversity-und-porno (German)
Online scavenger hunts	online - interactive; online - quiz	cyber bullying; social media; fake news; digital devices	Better Internet for Kids / Österreichisches Institut für angewandte Telekommunikation	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/online-savenger-hunts https://www.saferinternet.at/schnitzel (German)
Young People and Algorithms	offline	algorithms	Better Internet for Kids / Media Council for Children and Young People	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/young-people-and-algorithms https://medieraadet.dk/vaerktoejer/undervisningsmateriale/unge-og-algoritmer (Danish)
STOP cyberbullying paper folding game	offline	cyber bullying	Better Internet for Kids / Mannerheim League for Child Welfare	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/stop-cyberbullying-paper-folding-game https://cdn.mll.fi/prod/2023/05/19123808/mll_stop-nettikusaamiselle-kirppu-2023.pdf (Finnish)

Title	Type	Main Topics	Developer	Link
Fairy tales in the digital world (Bajke u digitalnom svijetu)	online - interactive	online safety	Better Internet for Kids / Centar za nestalu i zlostavljaju djecu	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/bajke-u-digitalnom-svijetu-fairy-tales-digital-world https://cnzd.org/bajke-u-digitalnom-svijetu/ (Croatian)
Quiz on Digital Games	online - quiz	online gaming	Better Internet for Kids / Landeszentrale für Medien und Kommunikation (LMK) Rheinland-Pfalz	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/quiz-digital-games https://www.klicksafe.de/materialien/quiz-zum-thema-digitale-spiele (German)
Board Game Kit Enhancing Media Literacy and Digital Skills Among Children in Latvia	offline	media literacy; digital skills	Better Internet for Kids / Latvian Internet Association	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/board-games-strengthen-childrens-digital-and-media-literacy-skills https://drossinternets.lv/lv/posts/view/speles-medijpratibas-stiprinasanai (Latvian)
GrooMix	offline	grooming	Better Internet for Kids / Child Focus	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/groomix-fr https://childfocus.be/fr-be/Presse/Publications/Ressources-et-outils/Post/11968/GrooMix (French) https://childfocus.be/nl-be/Pers/Publicaties/Educatief-materiaal/Post/11967/GrooMix (Dutch)
Cyberbullying - On a mission with Detective Shadow	offline	cyber bullying	Better Internet for Kids / Service National de la Jeunesse	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/training-primary-school-cyberbullying-mission-detective-shadow https://www.bee-secure.lu/de/training/cyber-mobbing-mit-detektiv-shadow-auf-mission/ (German)
Dressing up girl and boy	offline	child sexual abuse	Better Internet for Kids / CZ.NIC	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/dressing-girl-and-boy https://www.bezpecnyinternet.cz/cs/ke-stazeni/prevlekaci-panenka-ci-panacek/ (Czech)
Hooked? An escape room about your digital everyday life	offline	online wellbeing	Better Internet for Kids / Norwegian Media Authority	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/hooked-escape-room-about-your-digital-everyday-life https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/sites/default/files/imported_files/2023_06_26T08_53_39_91961931Z-230612_hekta_rapportering_engelsk--2d3a48e6-20bf-4fc0-90ad-9f44ef043c42.pdf (Norwegian)
Cyberactivity	offline	cyber security	Better Internet for Kids / NGYSZ	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/cyberactivity https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/sites/default/files/imported_files/2023_03_08T13_57_24_562442579Z-kiberactivitykartyak--c3bd8240-58cf-4b1e-b015-17e7dece6414.pdf (Hungarian)
Cybersecurity Quiz for Children	online - quiz	cyber security	Better Internet for Kids / NGYSZ	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/cybersecurity-quiz-children https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/sites/default/files/imported_files/2023_03_08T13_45_29_274249882Z-Cybersecurity_quiz--4190cb08-534c-4cf1-9f62-1324e7627e63.pdf (English)
Baby in digital age - paper folding game	offline	media literacy	Better Internet for Kids / Mannerheim League for Child Welfare	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/baby-digital-age-paper-folding-game https://cdn.mll.fi/prod/2022/09/19130942/mll_pienena_digijassa-kirppu-2021.pdf (Finnish)

Title	Type	Main Topics	Developer	Link
”Me and the Others” Videogame	online - interactive	online wellbeing	Better Internet for Kids / Centro Nacional de Cibersegurança	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/me-and-others-videogame https://www.internetsegura.pt/cis/eu-e-os-outros (Portuguese)
OK Groomer (roblox)	online - interactive	grooming	Better Internet for Kids / Child Focus	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/ok-groomer-fr https://www.roblox.com/games/11834339946/OK-Groomer (French)
Nude images in Chip reality - Interactive game for young people	online - interactive	grooming; child sexual abuse	Better Internet for Kids / Mannerheim League for Child Welfare	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/nude-images-chip-reality-interactive-game-young-people https://www.nuortennetti.fi/netti-ja-media/seksuaalinen-hairinta-netissa/peli-alastonkuvia-sirulottuvuudessa/ (Finnish)
Printable board games for children about internet safety	offline	online safety	Better Internet for Kids / Latvian Internet Association	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/printable-board-games-children-about-internet-safety https://drossinternets.lv/lv/info/materiali-nometnem (Latvian)
Spoofy	online - interactive	online safety	Better Internet for Kids / Association - Langas	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/cybersecurity-game-spoofy-lietuva https://www.spoofy.lt/lt (Lithuanian) https://www.spoofy.lt/uk (Ukrainian) https://www.spoofy.lt/en (English)
Board Game - Let's Discover the Digital World	offline	digital skills	Better Internet for Kids / Direção-Geral da Educação	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/board-game-lets-discover-digital-world https://www.seguranet.pt/index.php/pt/jogo-de-tabuleiro-vamos-descobrir-o-mundo-digital (Portuguese)
DIGIFIT inclusive game	online - interactive	online wellbeing	Better Internet for Kids / Mannerheim League for Child Welfare	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/digifit-inclusive-game https://www.mll.fi/tehtavat/digifitkirppu/ (Finnish)
Interland	online - interactive	online safety	Google	https://beinternetlegends.withgoogle.com/en_uk https://beinternetlegends.withgoogle.com/en_uk/interland (English)
Browsing information: An interactive quiz to learn as a family how to search and verify information on the Internet	online - quiz	online safety	Better Internet for Kids / TRALALERE	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/browsing-information-interactive-quiz-learn-family-how-search-and-verify https://www.vinzelou.net/fr/ressource/linfo-en-ligne-et-nous (French)
Cybersec cases vol 2	offline	cyber security	Better Internet for Kids / Estonian Union for Child Welfare	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/cybersec-juhtumid-vol2-cybersec-cases-vol-2 https://sites.google.com/view/tty-csgame/english (English)
An interactive quiz to help families talk about their use of digital objects!	online - quiz	social media	Better Internet for Kids / TRALALERE	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/interactive-quiz-help-families-talk-about-their-use-digital-objects https://www.vinzelou.net/fr/ressource/les-reseaux-sociaux-et-nous (French)

Title	Type	Main Topics	Developer	Link
#Flashtag	offline	privacy; sex and relationships	Better Internet for Kids / TRALALERE	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/promotiontutorial-video-flashtag https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/flashtag-fr http://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/flashtag-nl https://fb.watch/aaGduZVRf6/ (video) https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/sites/default/files/imported_files/20200120_102335657_272_Flashtag.jpg (French) https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/sites/default/files/imported_files/20200120_102322195_938_Flashtag.jpg (Dutch)
Necio.pl – exploring internet together – lesson scenario	online - interactive	online safety	Better Internet for Kids / NASK	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/neciopl-exploring-internet-together-lesson-scenario https://edukacja.fdds.pl/pluginfile.php/703/course/section/698/Necio%20scenariusz_ver%20intern-et-2021.pdf (Poland)
Cyber Trouble	offline	cyber security	Better Internet for Kids / CZ.NIC	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/cyber-trouble-game-pdf https://www.nic.cz/files/edice/Cyber_trouble_online_version_EN.pdf (English)
Online quiz 'Fake news'	online - quiz	fake news	Better Internet for Kids / Child Focus	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/online-quiz-fake-news-0 https://childfocus-trust.be/app/trust (Dutch)
Connected families, test yourself! (Online info and us)	online - quiz	online safety	Better Internet for Kids / TRALALERE	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/connected-families-test-yourself-online-info-and-us https://www.vinzelou.net/fr/ressource/linfo-en-ligne-et-nous (French)
Sextortion Escaperoom-suitcase	offline	online child sexual abuse; sextortion	Better Internet for Kids / Offlimits	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/sextortion-escaperoom-suitcase
The Star Colony - a computer game for families	online - interactive	online wellbeing; online safety	Better Internet for Kids / Norwegian Media Authority	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/star-colony-computer-game-families https://dialogduk.no/spill?la=EN (English) https://spill.dialogduk.no/ (Norwegian)
Board game with comics about different situations on the internet	offline	online safety; fake news; social media; digital skills	Better Internet for Kids / Latvian Internet Association	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/board-game-comics-about-different-situations-internet https://drossinternets.lv/lv/materials/download/spele-ar-komiksiem-par-situacijam-interneta (Latvian)
Cyber security crossword for children	offline	cyber security; online safety	Better Internet for Kids / CZ.NIC	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/cyber-security-crossword-children https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/sites/default/files/imported_files/20200325_073821213_81_Crossword_groups.pdf (Czech)
MediaMasters: serious game about media literacy for schools	online - interactive	media literacy	Better Internet for Kids / ECP	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/mediamasters-serious-game-about-media-literacy-schools https://mediamasters.nl/ (Dutch)

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Stop la violence	online - interactive	cyber harassment	Better Internet for Kids / TRALALERE	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/stop-la-violence https://www.stoplaviolence.net/ (French)
eFollowMe Game - Digital Footprint (Ψηφιακό Αποτύπωμα)	online - interactive	digital footprint	Better Internet for Kids / Cyprus Pedagogical Institute	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/efollowme-game-digital-footprint-psifiako-apotypoma http://efollowme.cs.ucy.ac.cy/ (Greek)
Info Hunter: the French pedagogical lesson to develop critical mind	online - interactive	fake news	Better Internet for Kids / TRALALERE	https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/resource-directory/info-hunter-french-pedagogical-lesson-develop-critical-mind https://www.infohunter.education/ (French)
RAYUELA (Portugal)	online - interactive	online safety; cyber bullying	Rayuela / Policia Judiciaria	https://www.rayuela-h2020.eu/ https://www.rayuela-h2020.eu/rayuela-game/ https://rayuela.pj.pt/
Get Bad News	online - interactive	fake news; misinformation; media literacy	TILT	https://www.sdmlab.psychol.cam.ac.uk/research/bad-news-game https://www.getbadnews.com/en
Cat Park	online - interactive	fake news	TILT	http://catpark.game/
Harmony Square	online - interactive	fake news	TILT	https://harmonysquare.game/en
Under Pressure	online - interactive	disinformation	TILT	https://www.getunderpressure.com/
Go Viral	online - interactive	misinformation	TILT	https://www.goviralgame.com/books/go-viral
OFCOM	online - interactive	social media	OFCOM	https://www.ofcom.org.uk/online-safety/protecting-children/piloting-serious-games/ https://www.ofcom.org.uk/siteassets/resources/documents/research-and-data/online-research/keeping-children-safe-online/serious-game/serious-game-pilot-results.pdf?v=328563 https://populuslive.online-host.solutions/ASP/P019714Cog2/login.asp?u3=Game
Cybermission	online - interactive	cybersecurity	US Department of Defense	https://www.cybermission.tech#!/page/home
Cyber Sprinters	online - interactive	cybersecurity	NCSC (UK)	https://www.ncsc.gov.uk/training/ncsc-cyber-security-for-young-people-english-scorm-v2/index.html
Band Runner (8-10)	online - interactive	online safety	CEOP	https://www.ceopeducation.co.uk/parents/articles/band-runner/
Zoe and Molly	online - interactive	online safety	Canadian Centre for Child Protection	https://www.zoeandmolly.ca/app/en/

Title	Type	Main Topics	Developer	Link
Cloud Chaos - NetSmartKidz	online - interactive	online safety	National Center for Missing & Exploited Children	https://www.netsmartkids.org/games/
CEOP age 4-7	online - interactive	online safety	CEOP	https://www.ceopeducation.co.uk/4_7/
FBI SOS	online - interactive	online safety; digital skills	FBI	https://sos.fbi.gov/en/
POPS	offline	privacy; cybersecurity	Foundation for Technology and Privacy Outreach	https://www.onlineprivacymatters.org/education-initiatives
CyberSafe: Good Game (minecraft)	online - interactive	digital skills; online safety	Minecraft Education	https://education.minecraft.net/en-us/lessons/cybersafe----good-game
Cyber Legends	online - interactive	online safety; media literacy; privacy	CyberLegends	https://www.cyberlegends.com/
Digital Passport	online - interactive	online safety	Common Sense	https://www.commonsense.org/education/digital-passport
NOVA Cybersecurity Lab Game	online - interactive	cybersecurity	NOVA	https://www.pbslearningmedia.org/resource/nvcy-sci-cyberlab/nova-cybersecurity-lab/
Reellife	online - interactive	social media	Childnet	https://apps.childnet.com/reellife/
Cyber Five	online - interactive	online safety	ABCya	https://www.abcya.com/games/cyber_five_internet_safety
CyberSpotLight	virtual reality	online safety; cybercrime	CENTRIC / YHROCU	https://www.meta.com/en-gb/experiences/cyber-spotlight-vr/6136654923113131/?srsltid=AfmBOorbeGao6-bonNqgC72B3wQzJnGqEbStDn1Vi8hYNMBtP7DmUxeh
Libertas Veritas	online - interactive	misinformation	Deakin University	https://apps.deakin.edu.au/library/dlm/twine/MisinformationGame.html
Fakey	online - interactive	media literacy	Indiana University	https://fakey.osome.iu.edu/
Reality Check	online - interactive	media literacy	Media Smarts (CA)	https://mediasmarts.ca/digital-media-literacy/educational-games/reality-check-game
Ask Me - Your online safety friend	online - interactive	online safety	UNICEF / Cyber Trust	https://www.itu.int/cop/askme/
Cyber Choices Challenge	online - interactive	cybercrime	NCA / Cyber Games UK	https://cybergamesuk.com/cyber-choices-challenge
Rock Defenders	online - interactive	digital skills; cyber security	NCA / Cyber Games UK	https://cybergamesuk.com/rock-defenders
Speak Out!	online - interactive	online safety	The Cyber Trust	https://speakout.thecybertrust.org/
SpaceShelter	online - interactive	online safety	Google	https://spaceshelter.withgoogle.com/
Play It Safe	online - interactive	online safety	Australian Federal Police	https://playingitsafe.org.au/

Title	Type	Main Topics	Developer	Link
Digital Explorers: An Online Safety Quest	offline	online safety	London Grid for Learning Trust	https://lgfl.net/safeguarding/online-safety/digital-explorers
Appyness	online - interactive	online safety	iSAFE Project / Zeeko	https://zeeko.ie/appynessonline/
Hate Hunters	online - interactive	hate speech	Extremismus	https://www.extremismus.info/hate-hunters-en
Decount	online - interactive	online radicalisation	Extremismus	https://www.extremismus.info/decounten
May and Bay: Online Child Sexual Exploitation and Abuse in Southeast Asia	online - interactive	online child sexual exploitation	Research Article	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s41134-024-00314-2
Using game-based learning to teach young people about privacy and online safety	offline	online safety; cyberbullying	Research Article	https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2023.2265424
Riskio: A Serious Game for Cyber Security Awareness and Education	offline	cybersecurity	Research Article	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2020.101827
CyberKids: video game for raising cyber security awareness in children	online - interactive	cybersecurity	Research Article	https://doi.org/10.1109/SCCC51225.2020.9281253
Children's Awareness of Digital Wellness: A Serious Games Approach	online - interactive	cybersecurity; online wellbeing	Research Article	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-80865-5_7
Design, Development, and Evaluation of a Cybersecurity, Privacy, and Digital Literacy Game for Tweens	online - interactive	privacy; digital skills	Research Article	https://doi.org/10.1145/3469821
Exploring empathy in cyberbullying with serious games	online - interactive	cyberbullying	Research Article	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104155
Serious games to prevent and detect bullying and cyberbullying: A systematic serious games and literature review	n/a	cyberbullying	Research Article	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.103958
Datak	online - interactive	online safety; cybersecurity	Radio Télévision Suisse	https://www.datak.ch/#/start

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